

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

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Executive Summary

The present document is a deliverable of the RECAP project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate – General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Innovation Action programme (H2020).

The deliverable presents the second version of the project Data Management Plan (DMP). This second version lists the various new datasets that will be produced by the project, the main data sharing and the major management principles the project will implement around them. Thus, the deliverable includes all the significant changes such changes in consortium policies and any external factors that may have influenced data management in RECAP project. It is submitted on Month 12 as a Mid-Term review of the RECAP Data Management Plan.

The deliverable is structured in the following chapters:

- Chapter 1 includes an introduction to the deliverable.
- Chapter 2 includes the description of the datasets along with the documented changes and additional information.

1. Introduction

The RECAP project aims to develop and pilot test a platform for the delivery of public services that will enable the improved implementation of the CAP, targeting public Paying Agencies, Agricultural Consultants and farmers. The RECAP platform will make use of large volumes of publicly available data provided by satellite remote sensing, and user-generated provided by farmers through mobile devices.

This deliverable D1.5 “Data Management Plan (2)” aims to document all the updates on the RECAP project data management life cycle for all datasets to be collected, processed or generated. A description of how the results will be shared, including access procedures and preservation according to the guidelines in Horizon 2020. It is a living document and it evolves and gains more precision and substance during the lifespan of the project.

Although the DMP is being developed by DRAXIS, its implementation involves all project partners’ contribution. The next version of the DMP, to be published at M30, will describe more in detail the practical data management procedures implemented by the RECAP project.

The Work Packages that have not occurred any changes are not included in this deliverable.

2. DMP Components in RECAP

2.1 DMP Components in WP2 – Users’ needs analysis & co-production of services (UREAD)

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	<p>Collection of user needs for scoping of the initial requirements (Deliverable 2.2) and also for the co-production phase (Deliverable 2.4), where applicable results will also be used to produce peer reviewed papers.</p> <p>Collating data from end users is an integral part of the RECAP project – co-production of the final product will help to ensure that a useful product is created.</p> <p>Questionnaire data (including written responses (.docx and .xlsx) and recordings (.mp3)) comprise the majority of the data. We may also collect previous inspection and BPS reports.</p> <p>The origin of the data is from Paying Agency partners in the RECAP project, farmers in the partner countries as well as agricultural consultants and accreditation bodies in the partner countries.</p> <p>Written responses are likely to be fairly small in size (<1Gb over the course of the project). Recordings are larger files and likely to be 10-20 Gb over the course of the project.</p> <p>The data is essential for the technical team to develop the RECAP platform; other partner teams throughout the project, as well as the wider research community when results are published will benefit.</p>
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>When data is published in peer reviewed papers it will be available to any who wish to use it. As it contains confidential and sensitive information, the raw data will not be made available.</p> <p>Data is stored on University of Reading servers and labelled with the work package, country of origin and the type of data.</p>
Making data openly accessible	<p>Data contains sensitive personal data therefore it cannot legally be made public. Anonymized, summarised data will be available in any published papers.</p> <p>Complete data cannot be made available because it contains sensitive personal data.</p>
Making data interoperable	<p>Raw data cannot be made freely available because it contains sensitive personal information. Data included in published papers will be anonymised and follow the standards of the journal to ensure that it can be used in meta-analysis.</p>
Increase data re-use	<p>Any data published in papers will be immediately available to meta-analysis. However, it is not legal to release sensitive personal data such as the questionnaire responses.</p> <p>Raw data contains sensitive personal data and cannot legally be made available.</p>

	Data quality is assured by asking partners to fill out paper questionnaire in their own languages. These are the translated and stored in spreadsheets. Separately, the interviews are recorded, translated and transcribed. This ensures accurate data recording and translation.
Allocation of resources	Costs of publishing papers in open access format is the key cost in this part of the project. During the duration of the project, money from the RECAP budget will be used to cover journal fees (these are approximately £1000/paper). Papers are likely to be published after the completion of the project, in this case the university has a fund to which we can apply in order to cover the costs of open access publishing. Data is stored on University of Reading servers.
Data security	University of Reading servers are managed by the university IT services. They are regularly backed up and secure.
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

2.2 DMP Components in WP3 – Service integration and customisation (DRAXIS – NOA)

2.2.1 System Architecture

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	A report describing the RECAP platform in details containing information like component descriptions and dependencies, API descriptions, information flow diagram, internal and external interfaces, hardware requirements and testing procedures. This will be the basis upon which the system will be built.
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	It will become both discoverable and accessible to the public when the consortium decides to do so. The report contains a table stating all versions of the document, along with who contributed to each version, what the changes were as well as the date the new version was created.
Making data openly accessible	The data are available in D3.1: System architecture. The dissemination level of D3.1 is public. It is be available through the RECAP wiki for the members of the consortium and when the project decides to publicize deliverables, it will be uploaded along with the other public deliverables to the project website or anywhere else the consortium decides.
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	Engineers who want to build similar systems, could use this as an example.
Allocation of resources	N/A
Data security	The Architecture report will be securely saved in the DRAXIS premises and will be shared with the rest of the partners through the RECAP wiki.
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

2.2.2 Website content farmer

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	<p>Various data like users' personal information, farm information, farm logs, reports and shapefiles containing farm location will be generated via the platform. All of these data will be useful for the self-assessment process and the creation of meaningful tasks for the farmers. The data described above will be saved in the RECAP central database.</p> <p>All user actions (login, logout, account creation, visits on specific parts of the app) will be logged and kept in the form of a text file. This log will be useful for debugging purposes.</p> <p>Reports containing information on user devices (which browsers and mobile phones) as well as number of mobile downloads (taken from play store for android downloads and app store for mac downloads) will be useful for marketing and exploitation purposes, as well as decisions regarding the supported browsers and operating systems.</p>
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>Every action on the website will produce meaningful metadata such as time and date of data creation or data amendments and owners of actions that took place. Metadata will assist the discoverability of the data and related information.</p> <p>Only the administrator of the app will be able to discover all the data generated by the platform.</p> <p>The database will not be discoverable to other network machines operating on the same LAN, VLAN with the DB server or other networks. Therefore only users with access to the server (RECAP technical team members) will be able to discover the database.</p>
Making data openly accessible	<p>Only registered users and administrators will have access to the data. The data produced by the platform are sensitive private data and cannot be shared with others without the user's permission. No open data will be created as part of RECAP.</p> <p>The database will only be accessible by the authorized technical team.</p>
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	N/A
Allocation of resources	N/A
Data security	<p>All platform generated data will be saved on the RECAP database server. Encryption will be used to protect sensitive user data like emails and passwords. All data will be transferred via SSL connections to ensure secure exchange of information.</p> <p>If there is need for updates, the old data will be overwritten and all actions will be audited in detail and a log will be kept, containing the changed text for security reasons. In case of necessary updates, the old data will be overwritten and all actions will be audited in detail and a log will be kept, containing the changed text for security reasons. The system will be daily backed up and the back-ups will be kept for 3 days. All backups will be hosted on a remote server to avoid disaster scenarios.</p> <p>All servers will be hosted behind firewalls inspecting all incoming requests against known vulnerabilities such as SQL injection, cookie</p>

	tampering and cross-site scripting. Finally, IP restriction will enforce the secure storage of data.
Ethical aspects	All farmer generated data will be protected and will not be shared without the farmer's consent.
Other issues	N/A

2.2.3 User uploaded photos

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	RECAP users will be able to upload photos from a farm. These photos will be timestamped and geolocated and will be saved in the RECAP DB or a secure storage area. The purpose of the images is to prove compliance or not. The most common file type expected is jpg.
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Metadata related to the location and the time of the taken photo as well as a name, description and tag for the photo will be saved. These metadata will help the discoverability of the photos within the platform. Farmers will be able to discover photos related to their farms (uploaded either by them or the inspectors) and Paying Agencies will be able to discover all photos that have been granted access to. The images folder will not be discoverable by systems or persons in the same or other servers in the same LAN/VLAN as the storage/database server.
Making data openly accessible	Only if the farmer allows to, some photos might be openly used within the RECAP platform as good practice examples. Otherwise the photos will only be only accessible by the relevant RECAP users.
Making data interoperable	Photos will be saved in jpeg format.
Increase data re-use	Famers will be able to download photos and use them in any way they want. Inspectors and paying agencies will have limited abilities of reusing the data, depending on the access level given by the farmer. This will be defined later in the project.
Allocation of resources	Preserving photos for a long time will offer both farmers and the paying agencies the opportunity to check field conditions of previous years and use them as example to follow or avoid.
Data security	User generated photos will be saved on the RECAP server. SSL connections will be established so that all data are transferred securely. In case of necessary updates, the old data will be overwritten and all actions will be audited in detail and a log will be kept, containing the changed text for security reasons. The system will be daily backed up and backups will be kept for 3 days. All backups will be hosted on a remote server to avoid disaster scenarios. All servers will be hosted behind firewalls inspecting all incoming requests against known vulnerabilities such as SQL injection, cookie tampering and cross-site scripting. Finally, IP restriction will enforce the secure storage of data.
Ethical aspects	All user generated data will be protected and will not be shared without the farmer's consent.

Other issues	N/A
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2.2.4 Website content inspectors

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	Inspection results will be generated by the inspectors through the system. The inspection results will be available through the farmer's electronic record and will be saved in the RECAP central database.
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>Metadata such as date, time, associated farmer and inspector and inspection type will be saved along with the inspection results to enhance the discoverability of the results.</p> <p>Inspectors will be able to discover all inspection results, whereas farmers will only be able to discover results of their farms. The administrator of the app will be able to discover all the inspection results generated by the platform.</p> <p>The database will not be discoverable to other network machines operating on the same LAN, VLAN with the DB server or other networks. Therefore only users with access to the server (RECAP technical team members) will be able to discover the database.</p>
Making data openly accessible	<p>Inspection results contain sensitive private data and can only be accessed by inspectors and associated farmers. These data cannot be shared with others without the user's permission. No open data will be created as part of RECAP.</p> <p>The database will only be accessible by the authorized technical team.</p>
Making data interoperable	Inspection results will be possible to be exported in pdf format and used in other systems that the local governments are using to manage the farmer's payments.
Increase data re-use	RECAP will be integrated with third party applications, currently being used by the local governments, in order to reuse information already inserted in those systems.
Allocation of resources	N/A
Data security	<p>All platform generated data will be saved on the RECAP database server. All data will be transferred via SSL connections to ensure secure exchange of information.</p> <p>If there is need for updates, the old data will be overwritten and all actions will be audited in detail and a log will be kept, containing the changed text for security reasons. In case of necessary updates, the old data will be overwritten and all actions will be audited in detail and a log will be kept, containing the changed text for security reasons. The system will be daily backed up and the back-ups will be kept for 3 days. All backups will be hosted on a remote server to avoid disaster scenarios.</p> <p>All servers will be hosted behind firewalls inspecting all incoming requests against known vulnerabilities such as SQL injection, cookie tampering and cross-site scripting. Finally, IP restriction will enforce the secure storage of data.</p>

Ethical aspects	Inspection results will be protected and will not be shared without the farmer's consent.
Other issues	N/A

2.2.5 E-learning material

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	As part of RECAP videos and presentations will be created in order to educate farmers and inspectors on the current best practices. Some of them will be available for the users to view whenever they want and some other will be available only via live webinars. The e-learning material will be mainly created by the paying agencies and there is a possibility to reuse existing material from other similar systems.
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Metadata such as video format, duration, size, time of views, number of participants for live webinars will be saved along with the videos and the presentations in order to enhance the discoverability of the results. All registered users will be able to discover the e-learning material either via searching capability or via a dedicated area that will list all the available sources. The database and the storage area will not be discoverable to other network machines operating on the same LAN, VLAN with the DB server or other networks. Therefore only users with access to the server (RECAP technical team members) will be able to discover the database and the storage area.
Making data openly accessible	The e-learning material will only be accessible through the RECAP platform. All RECAP users will have access to that material. The database will only be accessible by the authorized technical team.
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	N/A
Allocation of resources	N/A
Data security	Videos and power point presentations will be saved on the RECAP database server. All data will be transferred via SSL connections to ensure secure exchange of information. The system will be daily backed up and the back-ups will be kept for 3 days. All backups will be hosted on a remote server to avoid disaster scenarios.
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

2.2.6 CC laws and rules

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	Cross compliance law and inspection lists with checkpoints will be used both by the inspectors during the inspections but also by the farmers to perform some sort of self-assessment. The lists will be given to us by the

	Paying agencies in a various formats (excel, word) and will be transformed in electronic form.
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	All registered users will have access to the laws and the inspection checklists via the RECAP platform. Metadata related to the different versions of the checklists and the newest updates of the laws, along with dates and times will also be saved. Metadata will help the easy discoverability of the most up to date content.
Making data openly accessible	N/A
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	N/A
Allocation of resources	N/A
Data security	All content related to CC laws and inspections will be securely saved on the RECAP database server. All data will be transferred via SSL connections to ensure secure exchange of information. The system will be daily backed up and the back-ups will be kept for 3 days. All backups will be hosted on a remote server to avoid disaster scenarios.
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

2.2.7 Information extraction and modeling from remotely sensed data

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	<p>Collection of Very High Resolution (VHR) satellite imagery and farmer declarations. Generation of satellite based spectral indices and remote sensing classification products. Both data sets will be used to establish an alerting mechanism for breaches of cross-compliance. The products will be used in WP4.</p> <p>Processing of open and commercial satellite data for monitoring CAP implementation is in the core of RECAP.</p> <p>Data will be available in raster and vector data, accessible through a GeoServer application on top of a PostGIS database.</p> <p>Historical, Landsat-based spectral indices may be used to assist a time-series analysis.</p> <p>The origin of the data will be USGS for Landsat (http://glovis.usgs.gov/) and ESA for Sentinel, delivered through the Hellenic National Sentinel Data Mirror Site (http://sentinels.space.noa.gr/). Farmers' data and VHR will be provided by the Paying Agencies that participate in the project.</p> <p>Sentinel-2 data are about 4GB each, while Landsat around 1 GB each, both compressed. Assuming 4 pilot cases, and a need to have at least one image per month on a yearly basis, this accounts for 240GB of image data in total. Indices and classification products will account for an additional 10%, hence a total of 250 GB of data is foreseen to be generated. VHR</p>

	<p>imagery are of the order of 20GB in total. Vector data are a few MBs in size.</p> <p>Data and products will be useful for the Paying Agencies, the farmers themselves and the farmer consultants. They will be ingested by the RECAP platform and disseminated to project stakeholders, while their usefulness will be demonstrated during the pilot cases. VHR satellite data will not be redistributed, and a relevant agreement has been signed to ensure that these data are used only for the development and demonstration activities of RECAP.</p>
<p>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>The image data and the processed products will be available to all stakeholders through a PostGIS. Registered users will have unlimited access to the products for the duration of the project, with the exception of the VHR satellite data and farmers' declarations.</p> <p>Data is stored on the National Observatory of Athens servers and labelled with the work package, country of origin and the type of data.</p> <p>Geoserver and PostGIS provide a build-in keyword search tool that will be used.</p> <p>INSPIRE metadata will be created for all the EO-based geospatial products that will be generated in the lifetime of the project.</p>
<p>Making data openly accessible</p>	<p>Spectral Indices and EO-based classification objects will be made available. Commercial VHR satellite imagery that will be used in the context of the pilots will be restricted due to the associated restrictions of the satellite data vendor and the Joint Research Center (JRC). Farmers' declarations are considered to be Personal data and hence will be not open for reuse.</p> <p>Data and products will be made accessible through an API on top a Postgres database.</p> <p>No special software is needed. A user can create scripts to access and query the database and retrieve relevant datasets.</p> <p>The data and associated metadata will be deposited in NOA's servers.</p>
<p>Making data interoperable</p>	<p>PostGIS and Geoserver is a widely accessible tool for managing geospatial information. INSPIRE protocol will be used for metadata descriptors, the typical standard for geospatial data.</p> <p>No standard vocabulary will be used and no ontology mapping is foreseen.</p>
<p>Increase data re-use</p>	<p>The Postgis database that will be created in RECAP will be licensed with the Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL).</p> <p>The EO-based geospatial products that will be generated in RECAP will be made available for re-use for the project's lifetime and beyond.</p> <p>All EO-based products will remain usable after the end of the project, with the exception of the VHR satellite imagery.</p> <p>No particular data quality assurance process is followed, and no relevant warranties will be provided.</p> <p>EO-based products will remain re-usable at least two years after the project's conclusion.</p>

Allocation of resources	<p>Costs for maintaining a database of the EO-based products that will be generated to serve the pilot demonstrations are negligible. Publication fees (approximately €1000/paper) are however foreseen.</p> <p>Data is stored on NOA's servers.</p> <p>Long term preservation of the products generated for the pilots is minimal. However, if this is to scale-up and go beyond the demonstration phase, then making data FAIR will incur significant costs. Generating FAIR spectral indices and EO-based classification products for large geographical regions and with frequent updates, has a potential for cross-fertilization of different fields (e.g. precision farming, CAP compliance, environmental monitoring, disaster management, etc.).</p>
Data security	NOA servers are managed by the IT department. They are regularly backed up and secure.
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

2.2.8 Maps

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	<p>The following maps have been provided by the pilot countries and will be used by the RECAP platform in the form of map layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> LPIS (WMS or SHP) <p>The need comes from the fact that by using these maps, useful information regarding the compliance to the rules will be derived. All maps are not produced as part of this project but as explained they have been provided to the technical team by the pilots and will be reused.</p> <p>The types of the maps differ but some indicative types are SHP, SBX, SBN, PRJ, DBF, QPJ. Similarly, the size varies a lot, from 1KB to 20MB.</p>
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	<p>All registered users will have access to the above maps. The users will be able to identify the maps by their distinctive name.</p> <p>Metadata related to the different versions of the maps. Metadata will help the easy discoverability of the most up to date content.</p>
Making data openly accessible	N/A
Making data interoperable	Maps are saved in standard formats that are commonly used.
Increase data re-use	N/A
Allocation of resources	N/A

Data security	All maps will be saved on the RECAP server. All data will be transferred via SSL connections to ensure secure exchange of information. The system will be daily backed up and the backups will be kept for 3 days. All backups will be hosted on a remote server to avoid disaster scenarios.
Ethical aspects	N/A
Other issues	N/A

2.2.9 Examples of BPS applications

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	Examples of previous years submitted BPS applications have been shared with the technical team. As part of the user journey, the farmers will have to enter details similar to the ones they have entered in the BPS application hence the use of such data will allow the effective design of the DB as well as training material for the classifiers of the Remote Sensing Component. The data have been delivered in excel sheets by all pilots.
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	Only the technical team will have access to these data and will not be used on the RECAP platform. No metadata will be produced.
Making data openly accessible	N/A
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	N/A
Allocation of resources	N/A
Data security	All data are securely saved in the DRAXIS and NOA's premises.
Ethical aspects	No such data will be shared with anyone outside the consortium.
Other issues	N/A

2.3 DMP Components in WP4 – Deployment and operation (INI)

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	The WP4 data will serve to monitor the effective implementation of the pilots and provide the necessary feedback to ensure the RECAP platform is a useful product for the end-users. Previously available data from the pilot partners, especially with regards to the co-creation task in WP2 will be used. Also, data from D5.2 "Market assessment report" will be considered for defining the data to collect in WP4. In D4.1 "Pilot Plan", the metadata of WP4, procedures, templates and file formats for note-taking, recording, transcribing and storing data from questionnaires and focus group discussions will be developed and agreed. The main documents used in order to collect and generate the necessary data will be: informed consent forms, attendance sheets and minutes of the meetings/workshops, questionnaires, guidelines for interviews and focus groups, etc. Mainly and when possible, online and/or electronic archives will be used. Semi-structured interviews with

	<p>individuals will be collected and stored using digital audio recording (e.g. MP3) only if the interviewees give their permission. In case they deny, interview notes will be typed up according to agreed formats and standards. All transcripts will be in Microsoft Word (*.doc/ *.docx). Partners will be asked to anonymize the data prior to sending it to WP4 leader.</p> <p>The origin of the data for WP4, will be mainly from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Farmers from the different pilot countries <p>The size of the data that will be collected and generated in WP4 is not known yet, although written responses are likely to be fairly small in size (<1 GB for all pilots) and recordings to be larger files (10 - 20 GB). Raw data collected in WP4 will be useful for the improvement and validation of the RECAP platform. Once treated and anonymized, results of the pilots conducted in WP4 will be made public in D4.3, D4.4 and D4.5. It is foreseeable that data will be useful for the regional/national authorities of CAP in the pilot countries, for the agricultural consultancy services and for the farmers and farmers' cooperatives.</p>
<p>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</p>	<p>The raw data collected in WP4 will not be made publicly available as it includes confidential and sensitive personal information.</p> <p>Outline naming conventions used (e.g. Data_<WPno>_<serial number of dataset>_<dataset title>. Example Data_WP4_3_Intermediate Pilot Evaluation_Spain data).</p> <p>Data will be stored on INI's servers and labelled with the task name, country of origin and the type of data. Data will be searchable by country, task name and data type.</p>
<p>Making data openly accessible</p>	<p>All raw data collected in WP4 will be for internal use within the project consortium, as the objective of WP4 is to validate the RECAP platform developed in WP3. As raw data will contain sensitive personal data, the databases will not be publicly available.</p> <p>Data will be stored on INI's servers and it will be accessible through the RECAP wiki only by the members of the consortium. The administration of the RECAP wiki will only be accessible by the Coordinator of RECAP (DRAXIS) and the databases will be renewed when new data will be available.</p> <p>Raw data will be treated in order to produce D4.3, D4.4 and D4.5, which are public deliverables.</p>
<p>Making data interoperable</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Increase data re-use</p>	<p>The data of WP4 will start to be collected and generated in WP4 in the fall 2017, and all the specifications and periods of use, and re-use will be established in deliverable D4.1 "Pilot Plan" to be produced in spring 2017. As mentioned above, it is not legal to release sensitive personal data such as the questionnaire and interviews responses.</p>

	Data quality will be assured by asking partners to fill out paper questionnaire in their own languages. Interviews will be recorded, translated and transcribed to ensure accurate data recording and translation.
Allocation of resources	N/A
Data security	The data is collected for internal use in the project, and not intended for long-term preservation. The data will be preserved and shared with the members of the consortium through the RECAP wiki. WP4 leader (INI) keeps two daily incremental backups, one on a separate disk and another one on a remote server within Spain.
Ethical aspects	A letter explaining the purpose, approach and dissemination strategy (including plans of sharing data) of the pilot phase, and an accompanying consent form (including sharing data) will be prepared in D4.1 “Pilot plan” and translated into the relevant languages by the pilot partners. A clear verbal explanation will also be provided to each interviewee and focus group participant. Commitments to ensure confidentiality will be maintained by ensuring recordings will not be publicly available, that transcripts will be anonymized and details that can be used to identify participants will be removed from transcripts or concealed in write-ups. Due to the highly-focused nature of the pilot phase, many participants may be easily identifiable despite the efforts to ensure anonymity or confidentiality. In such cases, participants will be shown sections of transcript and/or report text in order to ensure confidentiality of their interview data.
Other issues	WP4 leader (INI) abides by the Spanish regulation in terms of protection of personal data (Ley Orgánica 15/1999 de 13 de diciembre and Real Decreto 1720/2007 de 21 de diciembre) and undergoes an external audit by a specialized consultancy (AUDISIP, www.audisip.com) in order to ensure that internal procedures of the company follow the regulation. INI has appointed an internal manager on Data Protection issues, who has put in place the necessary internal procedures to ensure the company follows the regulation and regularly trains and reminds INI staff on their obligations in terms of data protection and any modifications of the regulation.

2.4 DMP Components in WP5 – Dissemination & Exploitation (ETAM)

DMP Component	Issues to be addressed
Data Summary	Data collection is necessary for the elaboration of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy, the establishment and management of the Network of Interest, the Market assessment and the Business plan. Specifically, they are necessary for target groups’ tracking procedure and for Paying Agencies, agricultural consultants and farmers collective bodies’ profiling.

	<p>Regarding the types and formats of data collected, these are lists of communication recipients and target groups' lists in excel files containing organisations/bodies and their e-mail addresses.</p> <p>Parts of the lists have been developed in previous projects of the WP leader. The rest of the data has been developed through desk research. The expected size of the data will be approximately 7-10 thousands.</p> <p>Regarding the data utility, they are useful to the WP leader for carrying out communication and dissemination and for the development of the business plan.</p>
Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	The deliverables publically available i.e. "Communication and dissemination plan" and "Market Assessment Report" facilitate discoverability of data.
Making data openly accessible	<p>Data concerning e-mail addresses will not be openly available, as being personal data.</p> <p>Deliverables publically posted on the website of RECAP will make available all respective data.</p> <p>No particular methods or software tools are needed to access the data. Data are stored at ETAM's server. Deliverables are posted on the website of RECAP.</p>
Making data interoperable	N/A
Increase data re-use	As commented above, deliverables publically posted on the website of RECAP will make available all respective data without any restrictions.
Allocation of resources	Data management responsibilities have been allocated to two members of the WP project team.
Data security	Automated backup of files and no transfer of sensitive data.
Ethical aspects	<p>The pilot implementation and utilisation of the RECAP platform, requires the collection and storage of personal data. All data collected are kept secure and unreachable by unauthorised persons. They are handled with appropriate confidentiality and technical security, as required by the law in the pilot countries (Spain, Greece, Lithuania, UK, and Serbia) and EU laws and recommendations. The Privacy Risk Assessment deliverable was carried out to guarantee a privacy friendly platform i.e. a secure and safe environment for collecting, sharing and consulting personal data. The deliverable contains a chapter referring to the EU legislation. This is followed by a presentation of the laws and the competent authorities in the pilot countries. There is also a chapter that deals with the privacy risk assessment definition and characteristics. The personal data in the RECAP platform are discussed and finally, risks and mitigation measures are presented in detail. A glossary of terms at the end of the document provides useful definitions.</p>
Other issues	N/A

3. Conclusion

The DMP reflects the data management strategy and the procedure that RECAP will follow in order to identify issues and missing information related to data management that can be further clarified until the submission of the 3rd DMP. The DMP is not a fixed document but it will be updated once more during project lifespan (M30).

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
BPS	Basic Payments Scheme
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CC	Cross Compliance
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DMP	Data Management Plan
EU	European Union
IP	Internet Provider
jpeg	Joint Photographic Experts Group
mp3	Motion Picture Experts Groups Layer-3
LAN	Local Area Network
LPIS	Land Parcel Identification Systems
PDF	Portable Document Format
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSL	Secure Sockets Layers
VLAN	Virtual LAN
WMS	Web Map Server
XML	Extensible Markup Language